

Quantification of chemical species produced by the Surface Dielectric Barrier Discharge with liquid electrodes

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Results on quantification of chemical species produced in gas and liquid phase during the surface dielectric barrier discharge with liquid electrode depending on different experimental conditions will be presented.

1 General

Despite the quickly-growing applications of low temperature plasma physics and technology, many plasma processes are far from being completely understood, particularly the physical and chemical interaction of plasmas with solids and liquids. It is therefore essential to diagnose the fluxes of the generated species, to identify the relevant reaction pathways, to be able to tailor the reaction products for specific applications and to gain further insight into plasma-induced reactivity.

It has been previously reported that Surface Dielectric Barrier Discharge (SDBD) generating gas plasma at the interface with conductive liquids serving as electrodes was used for the treatment of hollow dielectric bodies such as polymer tubes [1-3]. Several potential applications of SDBD discharge were tested, but dedicated experiments under well-defined conditions is needed to better understand the discharge and to fully discover its applicability in emerging plasma technologies, especially for

material processing.

Figure 1. Surface Dielectric Barrier Discharge with liquid electrodes.

Plasma-treated liquids containing a mixture of various reactive oxygen and nitrogen species (RONS) with potentially beneficial chemical or biological effects are broadly referred to as plasma-activated liquids (PAL). Gaseous reactive plasma species such as OH, O₃, NO, and NO₂ are mainly responsible for the biocidal effects in plasmas generated in air [4, 5] and can influence the chemical reactions that take place during the plasma treatment of studied targets.

The aim of this work is to investigate the electrical discharge generating cold plasma with liquid electrodes, where the plasma activated liquid is created. Identification and quantification of the chemical species produced in the discharge and delivered into the liquid is performed.

Acknowledgement

This work was supported by Marie S. Curie Action Postdoctoral Fellowship under Horizon Europe with grant agreement number 101066764 and Slovak Research and Development Agency grants APVV-17-0382 and APVV-22-0247.

References

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